

MELCOR 2.2 iPWR LOCA type accident analysis, PART I: Thermal-hydraulics

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ABSTRACT

One of the coming Small Modular Reactor (SMR) designs is the integrated Pressurized Water Reactor (iPWR), which merges years of knowledge and experience in light water reactors with new demands from the market, such as flexibility, construction optimization, and reliability. Generally, SMRs are considered to be inherently safe and, in many cases, safer than generation III designs. Most of the SMR designs rely on passive safety systems at different levels of passive operation.

One of the ways to examine new concepts is a numerical simulation using a reliable tool. However, when new features come up, there are also new challenges for existing tools, even though they are continuously updated following the technology's evolution. To investigate if implemented new features give expected results and to increase knowledge about SMRs modeling and simulations, accident transients of iPWR were calculated using MELCOR 2.2 code and analyzed.

The work aims to understand better numerical simulations of the analyzed iPWR accident scenarios and code reliability. To do so, the paper is divided into two parts; in Part 1, the authors present MELCOR 2.2 iPWR input deck description, including nodalization and steady-state conditions as well as the analysis of an iPWR LOCA-type scenario in the design basis accident domain. In addition, design basis accident progression is compared to beyond design basis scenario in which safety systems are postulated partly failing. The analyses of beyond design basis scenarios in which core degradation is observed are published separately in second part of that paper.

The obtained results indicate that MELCOR2.2 can simulate the thermal-hydraulic response of an iPWR in accident scenarios. Values received in this study in steady state and accident simulations are mostly expected and coherent with general knowledge of accident progression.

1. Introduction

Interest in modern Nuclear Power Plants (NPP) is growing year by year. It is visible in the number of different licensing applications related to Small Modular Reactor (SMR) concepts in many countries (NEA, 2021). One of the popular designs is the integrated Pressurized Water Reactor (iPWR) which merges years of knowledge and experience in PWRs with new demands from the market, such as flexibility, construction optimization, and reliability (NEA, 2021). Due to this rapidly increased interest, many technical solutions need to be proven to ensure reliable operation and consistency with high nuclear standards. Safety is one of the key elements in the nuclear industry, which impacts costs, accessibility, and public acceptance, making it crucial to implement these designs into the energy market. One way to prove safety is to

perform multiple numerical simulations using different codes and approaches that characterize the investigated systems and unique new designs represented here by the iPWR. The analyses of the applicability of SA integral codes to iPWR is one of the goals of the European SASPAM-SA research project, described in the next section.

The nuclear energy is picked up as one of the solutions that could help fight global warming and reduce CO₂ emission (IPCC, 2018), while SMR technology is a one that could enhance the efficiency of nuclear industry deployment by decreasing construction costs and the risk of delays (NEA, 2021). The SMR concept has been known for almost 60 years, starting from naval propulsion reactors in 60's in USA, evolving through many different concepts such as test AVR reactor (Germany, decommissioned in 1988) (Gottaut and Kruger, 1990), or IRIS (International Reactor Innovative and Secure) terminated in 2009, till currently developing concepts, such as CAREM or NuScale (IAEA, 2022).

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Nomenclature

Acronyms

BDBA	Beyond Design Basis Accident	iPWR	Integral Pressurized Water Reactor
CDF	Core Damage Frequency	LOCA	Loss of Coolant Accident
CR	Control Rod	NPP	Nuclear Power Plant
CVCS	Chemical and Volume Control System	PCT	Peak Cladding Temperature
CVH	Control Volume Hydrodynamics	RCS	Reactor Coolant System
DCH	Decay Heat Package	RN	Radionuclide
DBA	Design Bases Accident	RPV	Reactor Pressure Vessel
DiD	Defense in Depth	RRV	Reactor Relief Valve
ECCS	Emergency Core Cooling System	RVV	Reactor Vent Valve
ESBWR	Economic Simplified Boiling Water Reactor	SA	Severe Accident
FP	Flow Path	SCRAM	Safety Control Rod Axe Man (emergency shutdown of a nuclear reactor)
HS	Heat Structures	SMR	Small Modular Reactor
HSG	Helical Steam Generator	TAF	Top of Active Fuel
		TH	Thermohydraulics

Nevertheless, even though the SMRs are not completely new as a concept, the advanced features they introduce to the nuclear industry bring additional challenges related to the licensing process or, in some cases, to numerical analyses. This work is done in the frame of the European SASPAM-SA project, which tries to address some of these challenges and enhance the analytical capabilities of the codes to predict selected SMR generic concepts to support future licensing processes.

The international and worldwide interest in this technology is proven by the numerous concept and ongoing developments (Carelli and Ingersoll; Carelli and Ingersoll). Based on the advancement of the particular light water SMR designs described in the IAEA report (IAEA, 2022), the five most advanced are mentioned below.

- CAREM (Central Argentina de Elementos Modulares) – type PWR, 30 MWe, CNEA (Comision Nacional de Energia Atomica), Argentina – under construction.

Designed by the CNEA, the main declared goal is enhanced safety and cost reduction by implementing integral design and passive system (Magan et al.).

- SMART (System-Integrated Modular Advanced Reactor) – type PWR, 107 MWe, Rep. of Korea, Standard design approval received from Korean Nuclear Safety and Security Commission (NSSC) in 2012 (IAEA, 2022).

The integrated reactor (100 MWe) designed by KAERI and K.A. CARE, includes eight independent helical steam generators and four reactor coolant pumps in the RPV to increase safety and reliability. In 2019 standard design approval of the pre-project engineering design and first-of-a-kind SMART construction in Saudi Arabia was submitted (<http://smart-nuclear.com/>).

- NuScale – type PWR, 77 MWe, NuScale Power Inc., USA, Received US NRC, Standard Design Approval in 2020 (IAEA, 2022).

The NuScale concept is a passive iPWR design that relies on natural convection with pressurize containment submerged into the reactor pool. The first builds are planned in North America and to be operational till 2029 (IAEA, 2022; <https://www.nuscalepower.com/>).

- IRIS – PWR type, 335MWe, design by a consortium of 19 organizations from 10 countries started at 1999.

Integrated PWR equipped with eight pumps, and eight helical once-through steam generators (Carelli et al., 2005).

- BWRX-300 – type BWR- 270–290 MWe – GE-Hitachi Nuclear Energy and Hitachi GE Nuclear Energy, USA and Japan, Pre-licensing process, undergo preapplication in United Kingdom, U.S.A., and Canada.

The BWR-300 is a natural circulation-based BWR type reactor with fully passive safety systems. Many features of BWRX-300 rely on approved ESBWR design. The first builds are planned in Canada (IAEA, 2022).

SMRs, even if they partially rely on experience from naval and research reactors, are, economically, technically, and even numerically (codes update is needed), an entirely new concept for civil and commercial usage. Because of that, they need to be analyzed carefully and widely with available tools and analytical methods applicable to this type of reactors. Considering the different SMR designs currently under consideration, several advanced features should be considered (e.g. containment process and interactions with the RCS, low pressure phenomena, phenomena related specifically to new system components or reactor configurations (Mascari et al., 2023) and available numerical tools should be used with caution, and integrated and system codes like MELCOR (<https://www.sandia.gov/MELCOR/>), ASTEC (<https://en.irsn.fr/EN/Research/Scientific-tools/Computer-codes/Pages/The-ASTEC-Software-Package-2949.aspx>) could be not fully validated for some SMR designs and features used in that type of NPPs. Despite ongoing research e.g. on helical steam generators or condensation in the pressurized containment (Mascari et al., 2011; Reyes et al., 2007; Lebel et al., 2022) the limited number of dedicated experiments available to the international community, operation and analytical experience, especially in a field of severe accident, force independent analysts to compare obtained results between codes to see potential discrepancies and uncertainties as well as limitations of the models. Due to that, many such studies are ongoing around the world (Nea, 2021; Skolik et al., 2021; Susyadia et al., 2019; Butt et al., 2016; Kima et al., 2011; Fakhraei et al., 2020; Li et al., 2017). These studies try to estimate the accuracy and usability of various numerical tools for SMR designs. Because of some unique SMRs features, like helical Steam Generators (HSG), application of passive safety systems, or submerged design, commonly used analytical tool need to be assessed, and even in some cases, new codes and models may be needed due to a lack of precise tools (Chung et al., 2012; Yeon-Gunlee, 2013; Xia et al., 2017). All that clearly confirms that SMRs could be challenging for existing analytical tools, which motivates to perform more dedicated analyses.

This paper investigates a generic iPWR characterized by a submerged containment and electric power of about 60 MWe. The model was developed based on publicly available data collected in the SASPAM-SA project and it does not represent any particular design.

Integrated PWR, conceptually, has Reactor Pressure Vessel (RPV) placed within Containment, which is submerged in a Reactor Pool (RP). One of the main features of such designs is small unit power and size (compared to modern Gen3 + NPPs), which theoretically decrease construction time with smaller entering costs, providing high operational flexibility. The integrated design, passivity, and a limited number of components should enhance the general safety of the iPWR concept (Reyes Jr, 2011, 2017.), and lead to decreased Core Damage Frequencies down to 10^{-8} or lower, which was estimated for such technology (Carelli et al., 2005; Campbell et al., 2019). This is achieved by implementing passive safety systems that rely e.g. on natural convection and decreased necessary equipment and piping. This iPWR design, allows coolant to circulate between RCS (Reactor Coolant System) and containment during an accident and increases heat exchange between the core and RP, which acts as an ultimate heat sink. Those systems are often inherently connected and difficult to simulate by severe accident codes, due to simplified numerical models implemented to achieve a reasonable balance between computation time and results accuracy. More details on primary/containment coupling in a reactor with a submerged containment and the related experimental characterization, publicly available to the international community, are in (Modro et al., 2003).

From the beginning, severe accident codes were designed to compute larger active systems, such as generation II reactors, for which many numerical models were initially developed. Passive systems are sometimes challenging to compute, especially natural circulation and convection due to small acting forces and lacking experimental data for code validation (Li et al., 2017) (Fakhraei, 2021). Fortunately, as codes are under continuous development, developers adapt them to cope with new technical challenges, resulting from development of SMRs and generation IV reactors (Humpriesa and Gauntt, 2018; Humphries, 2017; Humphries, 2018). For instance, as mentioned already, HSGs were not included in MELCOR models before as for typical nuclear installation, a simple tube heat exchange model was enough. Currently, it is already improved, and MELCOR could simulate heat exchange in the helical geometry. Also, simple natural convection could become a problem for SA codes as it relies on density differences between computational nodes. Codes like MELCOR average the thermal-hydraulic parameters through a control volume, which could easily affect phenomena like natural circulation, especially when temperature differences are not significant, and the nodalization is not sufficiently refined. For phenomena such as natural circulation especially in integrated configuration, correct nodalization is important to ensure that the results obtained are physical and simulate expected behavior.

A hypothetical postulated accident scenario and its sensitivity to a limited number of parameters were simulated and analyzed to investigate MELCOR capabilities, input deck correctness, and simple accident progression in iPWR. The steady-state parameters were compared with data from SASPAM-SA database to ensure that accident simulations start with the expected conditions indicated in the project database. The timing of main events was presented and analyzed between the different sensitivity calculations to demonstrate the impact of scenario assumptions on the accident dynamic. The analyzed accidental sequence is a LOCA-type scenario starting with the Chemical and Volume Control System (CVCS) line break, going from RCS to the containment. It is followed by SCRAM and, depending on the sensitivity case, the actuation of safety systems.

This part of the study focuses mainly on the thermal-hydraulic progression of the accident. It aims to identify the analytical challenges, differences between conventional PWRs, SMRs, and possible issues of the iPWR accident simulations. MELCOR2.2 was used as one of the most popular severe accident codes worldwide. It is an integral code that gives the possibility to simulate a whole spectrum of NPPs and accident scenarios, including the reactor pool behavior.

2. SASPAM-SA project

This work was carried out as part of the Euratom SASPAM-SA project. The project is described followingly (<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101059853>): “There is growing interest in Europe in the deployment of small modular reactors (SMRs). One type of SMR is the integral pressurized water reactor (iPWR), which is ready to be licensed as a new build. Despite the reinforcement of the first three levels of the defence-in-depth (DiD) approach, a sound demonstration of iPWR ability to address severe accidents (SA) should be carried out (DiD levels 4–5). In this context, the EU-funded SASPAM-SA project aims to investigate the applicability and transfer of the operating large light-water reactor knowledge and know-how to the iPWR, taking into account European licensing analysis needs for the SA and emergency planning zone. Project outcomes will help speed up the licensing and siting process of iPWRs in Europe.”

The SASPAM-SA project has been funded in HORIZON-EURATOM-2021-NRT-01-01, “Safety of operating nuclear power plants and research reactors”, and it is coordinated by ENEA (Italy). The project consortium is made of twenty-three organizations from fourteen countries. It must be highlighted that “it is not the project’s objective to assess the generic reactor designs selected but, based on the project findings, allow a more general statement on the code’s applicability to currently favored designs under postulated SA condition” (Mascari, 2022).

Two generic iPWR conceptual designs were selected to ensure that the project will cover a broad spectrum of evolutionary engineering features utilized in SMRs considered as most promising designs for European market. The design 1 is a iPWR fully based on natural circulation with compact steam generator, submerged containment, and an electric power of about 60 MWe; the design 2 is a iPWR characterized by the use of several passive systems, a dry containment and an electric power of about 300 MWe.

This paper addresses some of the SASPAM-SA tasks by analysis of design 1, with a focus on a) *identification of plausible SA scenarios for iPWR designs*; and b) *identification of the conditions in the vessel and in the containment that characterize iPWR SA scenarios and differ significantly from those in large-LWRs*.

3. Integrated pressurized water reactor (iPWR)

iPWR designs aim to increase safety by exploiting passive safety systems and, in the case of many designs, simpler and integrated structures. The idea is to manufacture independent pre-assembled modules that can be transferred and connected to the power plant, establishing multi-module nuclear power plants.

From the technical side, the focus is on minimizing the number of components like pipes and active systems. Conceptually, the RPV does not have pipe penetrations except for the feedwater, steam lines for the compact SG as HSG, and safety related valves. The mass flow in the reactor is driven by natural circulation, and in case of tube (or valve) rupture, a second vessel, the containment, can retain and circulate the water through the core, avoiding its uncover. The whole module is submerged in a pool, which acts as the ultimate heat sink (Fig. 1).

3.1. Codes description

One of the paper aims is to evaluate the capability of MELCOR for analysing iPWR and the applicability of the models for iPWR conditions as well as to investigate the sensitivity of the analysed accident progression on certain parameters and scenario assumptions.

MELCOR is an integrated SA computer code developed since the 80 s by Sandia National Laboratories (SNL) and funded by US NRC. It was designed to model and investigate the SA sequence in light water reactor nuclear power plants. However, it is under continuous development, and now it contains models that allow to simulate, for instance, non-LWR models, Spent Fuel Pools, or High-Temperature Reactors (Humphries

Fig. 1. Schematic design of a generic iPWR.

et al., 2019a; b; Andrews et al., 2019). In past years various models were developed and added to model light water SMRs, e.g. heat transfer models for helical geometry, and for Zukauskas heat transfer model for external cross-flow across a tube bundle. MELCOR is internationally recognized as one of the primary SA tools. Its main limitations are relatively long computational time and simplifications in implemented models related to radionuclides, chemistry, and rather coarse nodalization, which is widely used as best practice. It has been validated against various experiments and different plant designs as well as for SFP (Campbell et al., 2019; Sevón and Hillberg, 2020; Coindreau et al., 2023).

MELCOR is a full-plant integral code that makes extensive use of model parameters, allowing user sensitivity studies and increasing user control. Concerning the thermal-hydraulic models, MELCOR uses quasi-equilibrium models for stratified and well-mixed flow regimes. MELCOR is structured into packages responsible for different power plant features, representing the whole NPP together. The code could compute the thermal-hydraulic response of the modeled facility, the phenomenology related to reactor cavity and containment, core heat-up, degradation, and relocation, as well as the releases of radionuclides, simple aerosol physics, and hydrogen production.

3.2. Input deck description

The input deck of iPWR here studied was developed as generic iPWR, based on publicly available data only, which were gathered in the SASPAM-SA project into the design1 database (SASPAM-SA, 2023). Due

to that, many assumptions, simplifications, and adjustments were made, and it should be considered as an iPWR-like model, not a particular design. The unit with a power of about 160 MW_{th}.

The input deck contains three main sections, namely: RPV, containment, and RP, see Fig. 2. It has been proven to be stable, and it calculates the steady state in an acceptable range compared to the project database (below 3 % differences from the reference).

The input deck contains an Emergency Core Cooling System (ECCS) which is a passive safety system designed to mitigate accidental scenarios without external power or actions. ECCS here studied includes the Reactor Recirculation Valves (RRV) from containment to RPV placed between SG feedwater line and top of active core, and the Reactor Ventilation Valves (RVV) placed on the top of the pressurizer connecting it with containment.

A short description of the input deck below contains an overview of the main MELCOR components, called packages; for more detailed information about MELCOR, see (Humphries et al., 2019a; b).

3.3. Core model

Core in MELCOR is modeled mainly by two packages, COR and CVH. COR package is responsible for the material properties of the fuel, cladding, support, and non-support structures, including their dimensions, masses, and geometrical distribution. The COR package also includes physical models and parameters used during core degradation. The CVH package is responsible for thermal-hydraulic calculation and directly exchanges data with the COR and other packages (Humphries et al., 2019a; b).

The core in COR package has a cylindrical shape. The presented input deck is divided into 10 axial levels, where levels 6–9 contain active fuel, and 4 radial rings, rings 1–3 have active fuel. COR package mainly uses default values given by general MELCOR best practices for PWRs (Ross et al., 2014). The default Control Rod (CR) material release, oxidation, and eutectic models are used. The oxidation model used is the PSI oxidation model with default options.

The CR material release is done by creating three additional Radionuclide (RN) classes, IN-CR, CD-CR, and AG-CR and defining them into decay heat package (DCH) together with necessary Control Functions (CF) 7100, 7120, 7100 (Humphries et al., 2019a).

Material masses implemented into the COR package are estimated and defined in MELCOR depending on their functions. It means MELCOR distinguishes material used for support structures (important for structure integrity), and non-support structures like poison, fuel, cladding, etc. A typical PWR assembly was used to estimate all core related masses and geometrical parameters, considering the reduced lengths.

The CVH package in the core region is defined as 9 CVHs, two as a bypass, six as an active core region, and one for the Lower Plenum (LP), see Fig. 2.

The RN package is defined mainly by using default values. The hygroscopic model, convection option, and chemisorption model are enabled. Aerosols related parameters are set as defaults. The release model used in the calculation is Revised CORSOR-booth high burn-up. Two class combinations are included between Cs + I to calculate CsI releases and Cs + Mo to calculate Cs₂MoO₄ (CsM class).

3.4. Thermal-hydraulic model

The RCS is contained in the single RPV, which includes all necessary components, such as a core, riser, pressurizer, a primary side of HSG, a downcomer, and a lower plenum.

The whole Reactor Pressure Vessel (RPV) includes the core, the riser, made out of five CVHs, placed above the core; on the very top of the RPV is the pressurizer made with five CVHs. The primary side of SGs is divided into seven CVHs, and the downcomer into five CVHs. The RCS pressure is maintained by sprays and heaters placed in the pressurizer. Heat is transferred between CVHs via Heat Structures (HS). The HS used

Fig. 2. Ipwrmelcor input deck schematic nodalization.

in RCS is a cylindrical shape. Exceptions are top and bottom HS, which are defined as semispherical. The heat structure surface is calculated based on the general dimensions of the RPV.

SG helical tube design, here considered, differs from the classic PWR SGs. iPWR SGs are designed as bundles of once-through helical tubes surrounding the riser, placed within RPV. They are modeled as 7 CVHs for the primary side and 14 CVHs for the secondary side (7 for each bundle); see Fig. 2. Heat exchange is modeled using the Zukauskas HS model for an external flow (primary side) and the HelicalSG HS model for the internal flow (secondary side). Both models were added to MELCOR by developers in SNL to improve calculations of this type of geometry (Humphries et al., 2019a).

Containment contains 12 CVHs connected in a way that simplifies the simulation of natural convection. It means that CVHs with HS associated with RPV (receiving heat, on the left of Containment in Fig. 2) should generate flow up to the highest CVH where fluid is cooled down and comes down through CVHs connected by HS with the RP (on the right of Containment in Fig. 2). This kind of assumption allows the reproduction of natural circulation with MELCOR minimizing numerical instabilities. A similar approach was shown in (Campbell et al., 2019). The containment has been connected with RCS with, Pressurizer Safety Valves, and ECCS valves. Two additional connections in the input deck are related to accident scenarios, such as LOCA and LP breach after a potential melt-through. LOCA Flow Path (FP) is placed between the top of the core and the bottom of SGs. The LP breach is located on the bottom of RPV and connects RPV with containment and it is used in case of melt ejection.

The RP is made out of 8 CVHs connected similarly to those in containment. To simulate water convection, CVHs associated (by HS) with containment volumes were divided in such a way as to allow natural convection flow, as in containment. The floor and walls of RP are modeled as rectangular HSs. The reactor building is simulated as a single CVH with a free open path to the pool. The reactor building is freely connected with the environment CVH with open FL. The environment is modeled as a single CVH, set up as a constant volume with atmospheric conditions.

3.5. Steady-state

Steady-state was calculated for 3000 s before the accident to achieve stable and accurate conditions for the beginning of the accident scenario. The achieved steady-state, sufficiently agrees with the reference values to proceed with accident simulation. The main reasons for the slight discrepancies could be that data used for input deck development and reference data of steady-state are generic and developed on multiple assumptions in the project, which could bring slight differences. Also, it must be highlighted that user effect and the uniqueness of the design play a significant role in SA codes. That is why this kind of research is essential to observe potential major errors in input deck development.

In the steady state calculation, some difficulties appear during the stabilization phase in case of pressure on the primary and secondary sides. Due to the once-through helical geometry of SGs and the integral design relying on natural convection, pressure and mass flow fluctuations appear in steady-state. Using the dedicated helical HS models, Zukauskas and HelicalSG, helps to smooth out the system parameters. However, stabilizing RCS with heaters and spray systems was challenging in an integral design and needed multiple adjustments as natural convection-driven systems are sensitive numerically. The design 1 working conditions assumed in the SAPSAM-SA project are compared with those obtained from the MELCOR calculations results. The assumption was that the value is acceptable if discrepancies are below 3 % and the steady state parameters are well in line. The most significant differences are related to the HSG; however, as the inconsistencies are below 2 %, these discrepancies were accepted, especially as HSGs do not play any role in the investigated scenarios.

3.6. Accident scenario

The investigated transients are the Design Basis Accident (DBA) and the Beyond DBA (BDBA) scenario which is a hypothetical postulated SA sequence. First, a set of DBA scenarios has been identified for each design, to evaluate the capabilities of the codes to properly analyse the key TH phenomena in DBA conditions. In a second phase, SA scenarios have been selected to assess the code performance with respect to both TH and core degradation phenomena in SA conditions. It is worth to remind that the SA scenarios were identified based on the severity of the

accident consequences and not in terms of probability, since no PSA assessments were carried out in the SASPAM-SA project due to the generic nature of the reactor concepts considered.

The presented scenarios could help provide data about MELCOR capabilities to calculate the TH response of the iPWR design, its sensitivity to the scenario assumptions, and evaluate the severity of selected scenarios. This approach will also help assess the reliability of the input deck and the code and possibly highlight challenges for future calculations of integrated nuclear power plants.

The base scenario is a DBA scenario in which an initiating event is the CVCS line break, causing an LOCA-type accident. The break is causing RCS depressurization and containment pressurization due to water/steam discharge, which raises the water level in containment, actuating the ECCS. The RVV and RRV systems allow water to circulate between containment and RPV and conceptually provide cooling for the RCS under accident conditions. The feed water and main steam isolation valves are assumed to be closed just after break occur and they are fully closed in 10 s after the break.

In this study, authors also consider a BDBA scenario, including malfunction of safety systems in which RRVs are not open (no containment/RPV circulation allowed). In addition, a variation of the decay heat is included as a sensitivity parameter. In Table 1 all scenario sensitivity assumptions are described. The work is divided into two sections: the DBA, where ECCS system is working, and comparison of DBA and the BDBA, where there is a malfunction of the RRVs, potentially leading to severe accident conditions.

The CVCS elevation for all analyses was always the same, and only the opening fraction varied from 100 % to 10 %. In the BDBA1 cases the CVCS opening is equal to 100 % DBA case. In all scenarios, two decay heat tables based on ANS73 standard are used, scaled to the nominal power of the iPWR design. They are labeled as ANS for default decay heat, and increased by 20 %, labeled as ANS 120 %, see Table 1. All transients are analyzed for 48 h; however, in some cases, only part of the calculations is presented to make the analysis more readable.

4. Results

The following chapter analyses the most critical parameters during the simulated accident transients, including the timing of the events, as well as thermal-hydraulic response of the DBA part of the accident. In addition, one BDBA in which the ECCS is postulated to fail is included for comparison. More details of the postulated BDBA scenarios are given in the Part 2 of this paper. The results section is divided into three parts: i) the transient events, allowing to see the influence of the scenario assumptions on the timing/dynamics of main events, ii) the DBA, and iii) comparison of DBA and BDBA cases.

Table 1
Description of the scenario sensitivity assumptions.

Scenario	CVCS definition	RVV	RRV	Decay heat
DBA_10% DBA_10%_120	10 % of CVCS cross-section	available	available	ANS ANS 120 %
DBA_20% DBA_20%_120	20 % of CVCS cross-section	available	available	ANS ANS 120 %
DBA_35% DBA_35%_120	35 % of CVCS cross-section	available	available	ANS ANS 120 %
DBA_100% DBA_100% _120	100 % of CVCS cross-section	available	available	ANS ANS 120 %
BDBA1 BDBA1_120	100 % of CVCS cross-section	available	unavailable	ANS ANS 120 %

4.1. Transient events

Event timing is an essential indicator of the accident progression during the transient, especially for a long-term investigation. The list of main events with corresponding values and timing is presented in Table 2 and Table 4. The additional scenario assumptions that could impact the results are safety signal and valve reaction delays. For all relevant valves, there is an assumed delay from signal occurrence. In the Table 3 and Table 5 selected physical parameters are compared to highlight differences between sensitivity scenario assumptions.

The results were split into two categories, DBA and BDBA. DBA sequences are presented in Table 2 and Table 3. In these sequences, core uncover is not expected, and the main focus is on analyses of TH response. The BDBA and DBA100% sequences are presented separately in Table 4 and Table 5, as due to RRV postulated malfunction the accident progression could be more severe.

The Table 2, Table 3, Table 4 and Table 5 show that MELCOR calculations give coherent results and, based on the experience from PWR analyses, the expected dynamic of the transient. The events, parameters, and timing of DBA, Table 2 and Table 3, show that a larger break cross-section and elevated decay heat generally accelerate the transient. Some parameters such as the timing of the SCRAM signal or ECCS actuation, present less intuitive results. For example, with 20 % break, calculated SCRAM happens earlier than with 35 % break or lower decay heat actuates ECCS quicker (DBA10%). The mentioned SCRAM and ECCS actuation discrepancies are minor and related to the signal definition, which relies on high pressure in the pressurizer. The fast nature of the accident, especially at the beginning of the transient, could cause that difference, and related to the parameters fluctuations. All other values, like water levels and pressures, align with expectations of what should happen with higher decay heat or a bigger break cross-section. As long the differences are not significant and could be explained, results were assessed as expected, confirming the input deck’s ability to simulate more challenging scenarios such as BDBA.

The BDBA scenario, compared with DBA100% in Table 4 and Table 5, shows that results are similar. In the BDBA cases, despite safety system malfunction, there is no core uncover, H2 generation, or increase of Peak Cladding Temperature (PCT). An intriguing observation is that although the BDBA cases reached the TAF in 1 h after the break, and the DBA did not reach it at all, a higher PCT was observed in the DBA, which will be analyzed in the following BDBA sub-chapter. The PCT of BDBA is not mentioned in Table 4 as in the whole investigated transient, it does not increase above the steady-state value. The one main difference in BDBA is stuck closed RRVs, which cause the higher water level in containment and lower in RCS, however, with limited impact on the transient.

Analyses of the event’s timing compared to the scenario assumptions show that parameters like SCRAM, the response of containment or ECCS, propagate in line with scenario modification. For instance, a higher decay heat or bigger break cross-section accelerates the accident progression, indicating code and input deck capabilities to calculate such transient and designs.

4.2. DBA analyses

In all DBA cases, all safety valves (RVV and RRV) work, which allows water to recirculate from containment back to RPV, to ensure core cooling. The DBA scenario starts with a break (opening of CVCS line, Fig. 3) which caused quick pressurization of containment and depressurization of the RPV, Fig. 4. High pressure of pressurizer caused SCRAM signal almost immediately after the break, depending on the case, between 17–37 s. The ECCS actuation is triggered by high containment water level and the low pressure difference between RPV and containment signals, and occur between 339 s and 4705 s depending on the break cross-section. When ECCS is actuated, circulation between containment and RPV is established almost instantaneously, causing

Table 2
Comparison of main event timing in DBA scenarios.

ANS	DBA 10 %		DBA 20 %		DBA 35 %		DBA 100 %	
	100 %	120 %	100 %	120 %	100 %	120 %	100 %	120 %
Event								
Break opens [s]	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
SCRAM signal [s]	25	25	29	29	37	37	17	17
PCT [s]	27	27	30	30	38	1065	375	370
ECCS actuation	4380	4705	1830	1815	1060	1035	341	339
MAX containment pressure [s]	4400	4720	1855	1840	1080	1055	370	365
Highest water level in containment [s]	4405	4700	1860	1840	1085	1060	370	370
MIN RCS water level [s]	4410	4745	1890	1870	1120	1075	390	400

Table 3
Comparison of selected parameters between DBA cases.

ANS	DBA 10 %		DBA 20 %		DBA 35 %		DBA 100 %	
	100 %	120 %	100 %	120 %	100 %	120 %	100 %	120 %
Parameter								
Highest water level in containment [m]	6.965	6.588	6.986	6.937	7.074	7.054	6.831	6.838
Max containment pressure [MPa]	6.596	7.298	6.843	7.254	6.745	6.995	5.988	6.099
Min RCS water level [m]	3.850	4.479	3.892	3.861	3.946	3.922	4.771	4.729
PCT [K]	614.8	614.9	614.9	614.9	614.9	617.3	613.2	614.9

Table 4
Main event timing in DBA100% and BDBA1 scenario.

ANS	DBA 100 %		BDBA1	
	100 %	120 %	100 %	120 %
Event				
Break opens [s]	0	0	0	0
SCRAM signal [s]	17	17	17.75	17.75
High level in containment [s]	370	370	5580	5585
ECCS actuation [s]	341	339	345	340
Max containment pressure [s]	370	365	370	370
Water level TAF [s]	–	–	3955	3475
Water level BAF [s]	–	–	–	–
Steam circulation [s]	–	–	–	–
Min RCS water level [s]	390	400	97,560	106,801
PCT [s]	375	370	–	–
Max core damage [h]	–	–	–	–

Table 5
Comparison of selected parameters between DBA and BDBA case.

ANS	DBA 100 %		BDBA1	
	100 %	120 %	100 %	120 %
parameter				
High lvl in containment [m]	6.831	6.838	7.38	7.43
Max containment pressure [MPa]	5.988	6.099	6.056	6.178
Min RCS water lvl [m]	4.771	4.729	3.11	3.15
PCT [K]	613.2	614.9	607	607
Core damage [%]	0	0	0	0
Total H2 [kg]	–	0	0	0

temperature (Fig. 5) and pressure drop (Fig. 4), which will be discussed in the next paragraph. In all cases, after 48 h, the system stabilizes and cools down until the simulation terminates. However, to improve the readability of the figures, most of the parameters are presented only for the first 2 h (7200 s).

In Fig. 3, LOCA mass flow rate is presented. The highest flow is calculated for the DBA100% (150 kg/s) and the smallest for DBA10% (15 kg/s), which is expected. There is no significant impact of the increased decay heat in that parameter. Analyzing sensitivity cases, one can see a clear effect of the scenario assumptions on the other parameters describing accident dynamics. The biggest break cross section (DBA100%) led to the quickest pressure drop in the system, and it

reached pressure equilibrium between RPV and containment in 370 s, Fig. 4. The DBA100% also shows the lowest peak pressure as well as the level of stabilized pressure values, see Fig. 4. With decreasing break cross-section, accident progression slows down, but pressures in RPV and containment are higher. This behavior could be explained by less efficient cooling caused by a slower fill-up of the containment due to a lower coolant mass flow rate through the break. Another difference between 100 % break and fractional break cases is the impact of the decay heat. In cases with smaller breaks, the higher decay heat causes visibly higher pressure peaks. The reason why pressure conducts in such a way is slower pressurization of the containment in the cases with fractional break, which gives more time to build up a pressure difference between basic and elevated decay heat cases. This difference, expectably, leads to higher pressure peaks when decay heat increases. A similar difference is visible at the end of the transient, even for the DBA_100%, proving that the pressure difference between basic and higher decay heat is developing over time; hence, that difference is more visible in cases where accident progression is slower (smaller breaks). The mutual outcome is that higher decay heat increases average pressure in the system due to increased energy in the RCS. The DBA10% is the slowest out of all cases e.g. reaching RPV/containment pressure equilibrium or PCT drop, however, the average pressure and temperatures are visibly higher. The PCT for all cases is under 650 K, meaning that simulated cases do not lead to any core degradation phenomena. In general, PCT profiles on the right of Fig. 5 follow pressure behavior, and one can see that, similar to the pressure, all cases with increased decay heat lead to higher values.

The CVCS line break caused a release of the coolant from RPV to the containment, leading to inevitable water level decreases in the RCS. Fig. 6 presents the RCS water level for the whole transient (on the left) and for first 2 h (on the right). One can see that the RCS water level decreases rapidly and, in all cases, stabilizes in less than 5000 s, slightly above 6 m, which in the presented generic input deck is around 2.5 m above top of active fuel. The containment water level behaves accordingly, increasing rapidly and stabilizing at approximately the same level as in RCS, see Fig. 7. The elevation of water level stabilization is related to the attitude of the RRVs. When the coolant in containment reaches that high, there is a visible slowdown in water level increase, see Fig. 7. After ECCS actuation, the water level equalizes between RCS and containment, as RRVs allow water circulation between RPV and containment. Due to the relatively high-pressure difference between

Fig. 3. Mass flow rate through the LOCA break, DBA comparison.

Fig. 4. Evolution of the DBA RCS pressure (on the left) and containment pressure (on the right).

Fig. 5. Evolution of the PCT parameter for DBA cases for 48 h (on the left) and for 2 h (on the right).

Fig. 6. Evolution of the RCS water level for DBA cases for 48 h (on the left) and for 2 h (on the right).

Fig. 7. Evolution of the containment water level for DBA cases for 2 h.

such as pressurized containment or passive ECCS modeled in MELCOR, and work as expected seems to mitigate a presented accident.

The simulation and TH analyses of the DBA scenarios were performed mainly to investigate TH response of the RPV-containment system, safety system performance, and stability of the input deck. The main motivation to include DBA in this research was to confirm MELCOR 2.2 capability to model not only a SA type scenarios and phenomena but also pure thermal-hydraulic transients such as the DBA cases. The results presented above demonstrate that MELCOR 2.2 is capable of performing a stable simulation of the DBA scenario of generic iPWR design. However, due to a lack of experimental data or comparison with TH codes publicly available, it can only be concluded that the obtained results are in general agreement with the expected TH behavior of the PWRs. More analyses need to be done to increase the certainty of the abovementioned MELCOR capabilities, especially comparing results with dedicated codes with detailed models and relevant experimental data. Which is a topic for future, more detailed studies focusing on particular phenomena.

RPV and containment at the time of the ECCS actuation, the mass flow rate through the valves is extremely high compared to flow under stabilized conditions, Fig. 8. In the RRVs, reverse flow from RPV to containment occurs. This flow is causing a water drop in RCS and an increase in containment, which can be observed in Fig. 6 and Fig. 7. However, the reverse flow can not be fully assessed based only on one set of calculations done by one code as its origin could be e.g. a signal (too early opening of RRVs), or flow path definition. Based on that generic and preliminary study, it could be concluded that iPWR and its features,

4.3. Comparison of DBA and BDBA

The progression of the two BDBA scenarios is similar to DBA100% transient till the moment of ECCS actuation. In BDBA scenarios, RRVs which are designed to recirculate water back from the containment to RPV are malfunctioning by being postulated stuck closed. Thereby, steam is released from the RPV through RRVs, and water can circulate back to RPV only when reaching the elevation of CVCS (break) on the containment side. The primary analyses are done for 48 h. The BDBA1

Fig. 8. Evolution of the DBA RRV1 mass flow rate (on the left) and RRV1 mass flow rate (on the right).

results will be compared with DBA100% to show the impact of the RRV malfunction.

The LOCA mass flow rate in Fig. 9 shows no difference in the first two hours of the accident between DBA and BDBA cases. The minor differences occur after 4000 s, due to stuck close RRVs in the BDBA case; backflow from containment to RPV is possible only through LOCA when containment water level reaches the break elevation. That's why after 4000 s there is a visible LOCA negative mass flow rate, see Fig. 9 and the water elevation in the BDBA on containment side is higher (slightly above break elevation), see Fig. 10. This backflow through CVCS line break works like a recirculation valve, allowing water to enter the RPV, which helps cool down the whole RCS.

The containment and RCS water level in, respectively, Fig. 10, and Fig. 11 shows how the lack of flow through the RRVs impacts the water level. The containment level in BDBA slowly rises from ECCS actuation (~340 s) up to 4000–5000 s when it reaches the elevation of the break, stabilizing slightly above that level, leading water circulating back from containment to RCS. The RCS water level behaves the opposite, BDBA level is lower than DBA as more coolant evacuates to the containment due to higher elevation of the recirculation. In the BDBA the recirculation path is a broken CVCS line which is around 1.5 m higher than RRV in DBA cases. In the DBA case, there is a visible level increase in containment and a decrease just after ECCS activation, which is not the case for BDBA. The reason is additional suction through RRVs, which will be described in the following paragraphs. The BDBA case reaches the top of the core, but there is no core uncover. The effect of the CVCS line break elevation on the accident progression is explored in the part 2 of this paper.

The pressure in both vessels, RPV (Pressurizer) and containment, respectively, in Fig. 12 and Fig. 13 follow previous observations, thus equalizing right after the accident begins and staying equal till the actuation of the ECCS. Then, the BDBA shows slightly higher values between 500 s and 4000 s for elevated decay heat and 500 s–2500 s for base decay heat. Then, in long term, there are no distinguishing differences between DBA and BDBA.

The PCT in BDBA is even lower than in DBA, see Fig. 14. In the DBA the PCT peak occurs when ECCS actuates, RRV opening disturbs RCS water level and water circulation, which causes most of the differences compared to BDBA, as shown in Fig. 15. Downcomer mass flow rate fluctuations are visible in both cases; however, the DBAs minimums are much lower than BDBAs, respectively –263 and –307 compared to –182 and –116 kg/s see Fig. 15. The negative value means that flow is in the opposite direction than modeled; thus, instead of going down to the LP and following the design circulation path (through the core), it is flowing in the opposite direction. That disturbance in circulation patterns diminishes core cooling efficiency and leads to PCT increase in the DBA. The reason for these differences is shown in the mass flow rate of

RRV1 in Fig. 16 and RRV1 Fig. 17. In Fig. 16 one can see that when RRV is open in DBA case, it causes a negative flow lower than –200 kg/s. It means that water flows through RRV from RPV to the containment, causing the described above, coolant level variations, which lead to PCT differences. The RRVs for DBA and BDBA in Fig. 17 show the same performance with negligible differences. Note: only RRV1 and RRV1 are presented, as the rest of the valves behave similarly.

Based on analyses in this work, it could be concluded that the accident scenario with partial ECCS malfunction could still be mitigated under specific circumstances. However, it was also observed that MELCOR calculates higher PCT in cases in which all valves function as designed than when RRV stays closed. The higher PCT in the DBA scenario highlights calculation uncertainty and uniqueness of iPWR behavior, which confirms the need for further investigation. *Experiments to support model validation would be recommended.*

5. Conclusion

In this work, the major objective was the development of a generic but representative iPWR input-deck in the SA code, as well as analysis of the iPWR behavior under hypothetical postulated DBA and extended to postulated BDBA conditions. The presented study is part of the SASPAM-SA project performed in the frame of WP2, “Input deck development and hypothetical SA scenarios assessment (SCENARIOS)”, coordinated by KIT (Germany).

In modeling the iPWR equipped with a helical steam generator, difficulties appear in stabilizing and achieving operational pressure during the steady-state. Using Zukauskas and HelicalSG HS models helped stabilize it and allow stable and satisfying conditions for the beginning of the accident simulation. This shows that MELCOR is capable of stably simulating a steady state of integrated designs with helical SG. It should be noted that the input model developed in this work is under constant development as the modeling best practices are one of the goals of the SASPAM-SA project. The obtained steady-state was in good agreement with SASPAM-SA reference values.

The performed DBA analyses give information about TH of the modeled generic iPWR. It confirms that MELCOR and the input deck can simulate stable circulation between RPV and containment, also implemented logic, such as safety signal, time of valve opening etc., works as expected. Such analyses are especially vital for innovative designs with concepts and components not implemented in the classic Gen3+ designs. It also shows that SA code (MELCOR) can smoothly simulate DBA scenarios and in the future, it may be compared with more dedicated codes (or preferable experiments) to evaluate the accuracy of the obtained results.

The comparison of the DBA and BDBA cases shows that partial postulated malfunction of the safety systems, such as ECCS, has limited effect on accident progression, but it provides valuable insights. Postulated accident assumptions were not enough to reach SA conditions. The described impact of the RRVs opening, in the DBA cases, highlights that the safety valve opening could disturb natural circulation at the time of ECCS actuation, which in some cases could affect further accident progression. The higher PCT in DBA cases than in BDBA underlines that SA analyses of iPWR could bring some unintuitive results, and such sensitivity study could help to improve future analyses. Such results also show that scenario and model-oriented investigations are needed, which preferably should be supported with experimental work for code validation.

Nevertheless, the analysis showed that the input deck and code used in the study could simulate the established natural circulation loops both during normal steady state operation and DBA sequence. It was also capable of representing the effect of malfunction of the ECCS on the natural circulation loop. Obtained insights point out the direction of further scenario sensitivity study with varying locations of the LOCA break, possibly leading to a SA, presented in separate paper, PART II of this study.

Fig. 9. Mass flow rate through the LOCA break, DBA vs BDBA comparison.

Fig. 10. The DBA and BDBA containment water level comparison, zoom-in 2 h (7200 s) on the left and 48 h on the right.

Fig. 11. The DBA and BDBA RCS water level comparison, zoom-in 2 h (7200 s) on the left and 48 h on the right.

Fig. 12. The DBA and BDBA pressurizer pressure comparison, zoom-in 2 h (7200 s) on the left and 48 h on the right.

Fig. 13. The DBA and BDBA containment pressure comparison, zoom-in 2 h (7200 s) on the left and 48 h on the right.

Fig. 14. The DBA and BDBA PCT comparison, zoom-in 2 h (7200 s) on the left and 48h on the right.

Fig. 15. The DBA and BDBA comparison of downcomer mass flow rate.

Fig. 17. The DBA and BDBA comparison of the RRV1 mass flow rate.

Fig. 16. The DBA and BDBA comparison of the RRV1 mass flow rate.

The MELCOR capabilities to simulate accident scenario for iPWR concept was proven by providing consistent results for postulated scenario variations. However, despite obtaining satisfactory results in this study, authors believe the lack of best practices, publically available experiments, and experience in the area of iPWR modeling makes such analyses more sensitive to the user effect, and in more complex cases, they may be burdened by higher uncertainties than for classic PWRs.

The presented results motivate further work on that topic as it is essential to enhance understanding of potential code challenges as well as input deck performance which will help develop best practices for the iPWR modeling and possibly decrease the SA codes uncertainties.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

M. Malicki: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Data curation, Conceptualization. **T. Lind:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Supervision, Project administration.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

The authors do not have permission to share data.

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Disclaimer

Described work was done as a generic scientific investigation to understand better iPWR modeling and simulation challenges related with severe accidents in such designs. It can not be used as a particular design analysis, and it should not be connected to any specific product or technical solution.

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